

**ENSURING THE SAFETY OF OPERATIVE OFFICERS IN THE FIGHT
AGAINST ORGANIZED CRIME: MECHANISMS OF LEGAL AND SOCIAL
PROTECTION**

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Abstract. This thesis analyzes the problems of ensuring the safety of officers and undercover assistants directly carrying out operational-search measures in the context of modern threats from organized crime. The procedural gaps in the system of legal and social protection of the operative apparatus, in particular, the lack of immunity for professional risk and barriers to maintaining anonymity in court, are critically examined. As a result of the research, scientifically based proposals were developed for introducing the institution of "justified professional risk" into the Criminal Code, digitizing procedural anonymity, and providing psychological rehabilitation for operative officers.

Keywords: *operational-search activity, organized crime, safety of operative officers, professional risk, undercover infiltration, undercover assistants, procedural anonymity, psychological rehabilitation.*

Modern organized crime, particularly large syndicates involved in transnational human trafficking, drug trafficking, and arms trafficking, poses not only an intellectual and technological threat to the state's law enforcement agencies but also a direct physical and psychological one. In the context of the intensification of transnational crime and the expansion of their counterintelligence capabilities, operational officers and secret assistants directly engaged in operational-search activities (OSF) are operating under the highest victimogenic risk.

The practice of "rapid access," aimed at the early detection of the activities of organized criminal groups (OCG) and their exposure from the inside, requires not only high professionalism from the employee, but also constant risk to their life and health. According to research by foreign and domestic criminologists, as well as specialists studying police psychology, operatives who are involved in a criminal environment or come into direct contact with the leaders of an organized crime group experience strong processes of psychological deformation due to constant stress, hesitation, and life-threatening circumstances. In the context of the professionalization of crime, it is a criminological necessity for the state to

create a solid shield of legal and social guarantees to protect law enforcement officers, particularly their secret apparatus.¹

However, in our current operational-search legislation, the mechanisms for the procedural, legal, and social protection of operational officers remain fragmented and generally declarative in nature. One of the biggest problems is that the institution of "reasonable professional risk" is not fully detailed in national criminal law. This situation leaves operatives, who act under the obligation to preserve their legend, legally vulnerable and often leads to accusations of "provocation."² Furthermore, the system for maintaining the confidentiality of employees' personal data, protecting their family members from criminal retribution, and providing full socio-financial guarantees in emergency situations (such as bodily injuries or deaths) does not fully meet the scale of transnational threats.

Therefore, the primary objective of this study is to conduct a profound scientific analysis of legislative gaps in ensuring the safety of operational staff directly involved in the front lines of the fight against organized crime, as well as to develop substantiated proposals for improving institutional mechanisms for their legal and social protection (including through the introduction of immunity norms into criminal legislation).

The most complex and high-criminogenic risk area of operational-search activities is the recruitment of undercover officers into the internal ranks of organized crime groups. Modern criminological and procedural practice shows that the system of protection for operatives and covert assistants remains largely mired in three major legal and organizational problems: a lack of legal immunity, the risk of procedural disclosure of personal data, and the absence of a socio-psychological rehabilitation institution.

The first and most fundamental problem is the legal vulnerability of the operative under conditions of imitation of a crime and "reasonable professional risk." In order to gain the trust of the criminal network and confirm his "legend" an employee secretly involved in the activities of a criminal group is forced to participate in the group's illegal activities under certain circumstances. For example, a facilitator included in a drug cartel may be involved in the transportation of narcotic substances. Professor E. Joe from the USA calls this situation the "paradox of violating the law in order to protect the law" and

¹ Bobrov V.G. (2009). The concept and essence of operational-search activities. – M.: YuI MVD RF, pp. 77-82.

² Baskov V.I. (2001). Operational-search activities: Educational and methodological manual. – M.: BEK, pp. 145-149.

emphasizes that the state, when giving an "illegal order" to its employee, must provide an absolute legal guarantee that he will not be held accountable.³

However, the national Criminal Code does not specify a specific norm (professional risk immunity) that excludes these forced actions of operatives as a crime. As a result, in investigative practice, the actions of the operative are often incorrectly qualified as a "provocation," and there is a risk of initiating a criminal case against the employees themselves. According to the renowned criminologist V.S. Ovchinsky, such a legal gap paralyzes the operational apparatus and forces employees to exercise unjustifiable caution⁴.

The second problem is the weakness of mechanisms for protecting the identity of the operative and their family members from procedural criminal retaliation. A distinctive feature of organized crime, especially transnational networks, is that they have their own corrupt informants within law enforcement agencies⁵. After the criminal case reaches the court, according to the principle of adversarial proceedings, in many cases there is a risk that the identity of the witness or confidential assistant will be disclosed by lawyers or defendants.

The research of the Australian scientist J. Bratuite shows that after the exposure of transnational criminal groups, their primary goal is to physically destroy the person who provided operational information or the secret agent, or to force them to renounce their testimony in court by threatening their family. Although "witness protection" programs exist in the legislation, a mechanism for ensuring the absolute anonymity of active operatives and their participation in court remotely (with full voice and image encryption) has not yet been fully implemented⁶.

The third problem is the imbalance between the system of psychological rehabilitation for operational personnel and the system of socio-financial guarantees. An employee who is placed in an UIG environment works under not only physical but also immense psychological pressure. Research by the English psychologist C. McLeod confirms that an employee who has lived in a criminal

³ Joh, E. E. (2009). *Breaking the Law to Enforce It: Undercover Police Participation in Crime*. Stanford Law Review, 62(1), P. 155-198.

⁴ Ovchinskiy V.S. (2001). *Fundamentals of Combating Organized Crime*. – M.: INFRA-M, pp. 240-245.

⁵ Reuter, P. (1983). *Disorganized Crime: The Economics of the Visible Hand*. MIT Press, P. 175-180.

⁶ Azarov V.A., Tarasov A.A. et al. (2018): *Use of RIA results in proving criminal cases*. – M.: Yurlitinform, pp. 185-190.

subculture for a long time develops value deformation and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).⁷

In our national practice, there are no institutional centers for the mandatory psychological rehabilitation of operational personnel after the completion of special operations. Furthermore, financial compensation and insurance payments in the event of an employee's death or disability in the line of duty do not fully correspond to the actual economic equivalent of the risk in the fight against organized crime.

Criminological, criminal-legal, and organizational-tactical analyses have shown that, amidst the growing transnational threats of organized crime, the existing mechanisms for the legal and social protection of operational staff on the front lines of the fight against them are insufficient. The main factors sharply reducing the effectiveness of operational-search activities are the lack of criminal-legal immunity for the actions of employees under conditions of "professional risk" and the imperfection of the system for maintaining confidentiality in judicial proceedings.

In order to guarantee the safety of operational staff and secret assistants and strengthen the proactive mechanism for combating organized crime, the following scientific and practical proposals are put forward:

First, the introduction of the institution of "Reasonable professional risk" into the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is necessary to supplement the chapter of the Criminal Code regarding circumstances excluding the criminality of an act with a special norm. According to this norm, it must be strictly established that an operative or a secret assistant is fully exempt from criminal liability for less serious crimes (imitation of a crime) committed forcibly to preserve their legend within the framework of the "rapid entry" measure to prevent serious or especially serious crimes and expose an organized criminal group.

Second, digitalization of the mechanism for ensuring the absolute anonymity of operational officers in the Criminal Procedure Code. Introducing into legislation as a mandatory rule the procedure for interrogating operatives and secret agents as witnesses in court sessions for cases of serious and especially serious crimes exclusively via remote video conferencing (special programs that fully encrypt/transform voice and appearance). At the same time, full

⁷ Macleod, C. (1995). *The Psychological Impact of Undercover Policing*. Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology, 10(1), P. 20-26.

confidentiality of their personal data from lawyers and defendants must be guaranteed.

1. **Third**, the creation of an institutional system for the social and psychological rehabilitation of operational personnel. Implementation of mandatory psychological rehabilitation programs for employees of the internal affairs bodies who participated in long-term and dangerous operational activities (including activities to infiltrate the criminal environment). Also, revising the amount of life and health insurance payments for employees of organized crime units in accordance with the level (coefficient) of real criminogenic risk in their activities.